

THE ROLE OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN ENSURING CITIZENS' RIGHT TO HEALTHCARE

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In the Concept for the Development of the Healthcare System of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019–2025, priority tasks were identified such as the improvement of national legislation in the field, increasing the efficiency, quality, and accessibility of medical care, expanding private healthcare, introducing mechanisms of public–private partnership (PPP), promoting medical tourism to attract investments, as well as the widespread implementation of electronic healthcare systems.

The development of market relations in the healthcare system is reflected in the transformation of the economic structure of medical institutions, their privatization, and withdrawal from exclusive state ownership. Alongside state institutions, the establishment of medical joint-stock companies, non-profit entities, and private medical organizations based on diverse forms of ownership is envisaged.

Currently, the number of private medical institutions in Uzbekistan continues to increase day by day. This fosters healthy competition in the healthcare sector, enhances the quality of medical services provided to the population, and contributes to the reduction of prices.

Pursuant to the relevant decisions of the Head of State, private medical organizations have been granted the opportunity to obtain licenses in 129 medical specializations. The legal foundations for public–private partnership in healthcare have been established, with particular emphasis on attracting foreign investments, expanding access for the population to high-tech medical services and equipment, and stimulating the participation of the non-state sector. Moreover, private medical institutions have been authorized to perform complex surgical operations such as organ transplantation. Conditions have also been created for the development of “Nursing Practice” and “Mobile Medicine.”

As a result, the number of private medical organizations increased from 3,000 to 8,500; the number of licensed medical specializations granted to private healthcare providers expanded from 50 to 129; the range of products manufactured by domestic pharmaceutical enterprises grew from 2,644 to 3,600 items, including an increase in the number of medicinal products from 2,556 to 3,096, medical supplies from 49 to 419, and medical equipment products from 29 to 85.

In his report, the former Minister of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, A. Inoyatov, emphasized that systematic efforts are being undertaken to gradually

transfer the functions of state medical institutions to the private sector. It was highlighted that the share of private sector participation in healthcare services is planned to increase from the current 20 percent to 35 percent by 2025, and to 60 percent by 2030, with the introduction of purchasing medical services from the private sector within the framework of guaranteed medical care¹.

For the successful development of this sector, it is necessary to foster the emergence of medical institutions based on various forms of ownership competing with each other, to form and advance the medical services market, as well as to encourage the establishment of joint medical institutions on the basis of foreign investments.

The system of public-private partnership (PPP) is considered one of the most effective mechanisms in the development of the private sector. Therefore, the number of facilities established in different spheres on the basis of PPP has been steadily increasing year by year.

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The system of public-private partnership (PPP) is regarded as one of the most effective mechanisms for developing the private sector. Consequently, the number of facilities established in various fields on the basis of PPP has been steadily increasing from year to year.

The Presidential Resolution of April 16, 2019, "On measures for the development of public-private partnership in the healthcare sector", as well as the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of May 10, 2019, "On Public-Private Partnership", serve as important legal foundations for regulating activities in this sphere and for the introduction of PPP mechanisms in the healthcare system.

According to Article 3 of the Law on Public-Private Partnership, PPP is defined as "a legally formalized cooperation between a public partner and a private partner, established for a specific period of time and based on pooling their resources for the implementation of a PPP project."

The interpretation and application of this concept in the healthcare sector has been the subject of research not only by national scholars but also by a number of foreign researchers over the past decade.

A group of scholars (Ahadzi M., Bowles G., Bennett J., Iossa E., Chen B.R., U.S. Chiu, Engel E., Fischer R., & Galetovic A., Greco L.) advance the notion of PPP within the framework of contract theory. In this interpretation, PPP emerges as a complex project, for instance, an infrastructure project encompassing multiple specific issues (such as the construction of a facility and the provision of

¹ uza.uz/uz/posts/sogliqni-saqdash-sohasida-xususiy-sektor-faolligini-oshirish-davr-labji_498682?ysclid=meqt08lxjw973901175

technical services). In such cases, the state decides whether to transfer all or part of these issues to a private company and selects the most suitable contractual model for operation. This implies that the project is divided into distinct components.

Meanwhile, another group of scholars (Hernandez-Aguado I., Zaragoza G.A.) propose interpreting PPP as a form of joint implementation of a specific project².

Turning to international experience, the development of public-private partnership (PPP) in the healthcare sector in developed countries dates back to the late twentieth century. As noted in an article by M. Torchia and A. Calabrò devoted to the Italian experience in this field, “Over the past decade, healthcare systems have been undergoing rapid changes due to the increase in healthcare expenditures and the reduction of state budgets. Nevertheless, management and project-planning challenges in this sector remain evident in Italy”³.

It should also be noted that in recent years national scholars have conducted research on the issues of public-private partnership in the healthcare sector. Among them, one may highlight the works of Y. Aliev⁴, B. Ochilova⁵, A. Khojanazarov, S⁶. Allamuratov, S.S. Ghulomov and others.

In the healthcare sector, as well as in all other designated areas, the fundamental principles of public-private partnership (PPP) are as follows:

- equality of the public partner and the private partner before the law;
- transparency of rules and procedures in the implementation of PPP;
- competitiveness and impartiality in the selection of a private partner;
- prohibition of discrimination;
- prohibition of corruption.

It is well known that the public and private partners are equal parties. The rules and procedures of PPP must be open, transparent, and comprehensible for all stakeholders. The public partner is obliged to ensure free access to information concerning the rules and procedures of PPP as stipulated by the relevant legislative acts.

One of the fundamental principles ensuring the successful functioning of PPP is the principle of non-discrimination. This principle is guaranteed through the following:

- equality of rights for participants in tender procedures;
- impartiality in the selection of a private partner;
- openness in the process of selecting a private partner.

² Hernandez-Aguado I., Zaragoza G. A. Support of public-private partnerships in health promotion and conflicts of interest //BMJ open. – 2016. – Т. 6. – №. 4.

³ Torchia M., Calabrò A. Increasing the governance standards of public-private partnerships in healthcare. Evidence from Italy //Public organization review. – 2018. – Т. 18. – №. 1. – С. 93-110.

⁴ Aliyev Y. Минтақавий туристик-рекреацион мажмуаларни ташкил этишда давлат-хусусий шерикчилик тизимини ривожлантириш //Архив научных исследований. – 2020. – №. 19.

⁵ Ochilova B., Nazarqosimov S. Ўзбекистонда “давлат дастурлари” ижтимоий соҳасини ривожлантириш омили //Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI. – 2020.

⁶ Khuzhanazarov A. Z., Allamuratov S. A. Look at medicine attention: problems and solutions //Ўтмишга назар журнали. – 2019. – Т. 24. – №. 2.

Furthermore, the requirements concerning the rules and procedures of PPP must exclude corruption-related offenses and ensure the implementation of preventive measures against corruption and its underlying causes, which, beyond doubt, contributes to the prosperity of society.

In their research, A. Ballantyne and C. Stewart identify four distinctive values as the fundamental principles of public-private partnership in the healthcare sector: public interest, governance, transparency, and collaboration⁷.

Turning to the specific principles of public-private partnership (PPP) in the healthcare sector, we may refer to paragraph 3 of the Regulation on Public-Private Partnership in Healthcare, annexed to the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4290 of April 16, 2019, "On Measures for the Development of Public-Private Partnership in Healthcare". According to this provision, the main principles are:

the primacy of public interest;

legality;

openness and transparency of information regarding PPP, with the exception of information constituting state secrets and other secrets protected by law;

non-discrimination and equality of rights of the parties to the PPP agreement;

and others.

In the context of healthcare, the primacy of public interest implies that every project or proposed concept must first and foremost correspond to public needs and bring social benefit. This is because the implementation of services such as designing, constructing, reconstructing, organizing, equipping, modernizing, financing, and maintaining healthcare infrastructure is directly linked to the protection of citizens' health, i.e., to the interests of society as a whole.

In Europe, PPP projects have been applied in various sectors of construction as well as in the realization of large-scale national projects. For instance, in France, cooperation between the state and the private sector on the basis of concession was first implemented in 1552 in the construction of a canal. However, such partnerships became particularly widespread in the 18th-19th centuries.

In Germany, public-private partnership (PPP) projects are implemented in various forms. In the construction of public facilities such as hospitals, schools, administrative buildings, sports complexes, and prisons, the state organization — as one party to the PPP agreement — often retains ownership rights over the immovable property, while transferring to the private investor, as the other party, the rights to construct and operate the facility for public purposes⁸.

⁷ Ballantyne A., Stewart C. Big data and public-private partnerships in healthcare and research //Asian Bioethics Review. – 2019. – T. 11. – №. 3. – С. 315-326.

⁸ This model is known, generally, as a build-transfer-operate model. In many cases, the public authority will already be

In Japan, 80% of hospitals are privately owned, while a unified medical service fee schedule, set by the state once every two years, applies nationwide. As a result, citizens covered by compulsory health insurance are free to choose between public and private hospitals. In order to attract patients, hospitals strive to operate in a competitive environment by ensuring the availability of highly qualified personnel and equipping facilities with modern technologies.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that it is necessary to transfer certain functions or services of state medical institutions to entrepreneurial entities on an outsourcing basis, as well as to implement effective mechanisms of public oversight over the activities of non-state medical institutions.

